

Angel investments as the most actual way of investment.

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Abstract: The article analyzes the institution of angel investments as an important mechanism for financing startups and innovative projects at early stages of development. The key characteristics of business angels, their role in the venture capital ecosystem, as well as the main models of interaction between investors and startups are considered. Special attention is paid to the problems and peculiarities of legal regulation of angel investments in various jurisdictions, including the issues of concluding investment agreements, protecting investors' rights and ensuring transparency of transactions. The paper conducts a comparative legal analysis of existing regulatory approaches, identifies legal gaps and proposes directions for improving the legislation to promote the development of the institution of angel investment. The results of the research can be useful both for practicing lawyers and investors, and for legislators and developers of the state investment policy.

Keywords: investment activity, venture capital, angel investor, startup, option.

Angel investment is a form of financing in which private investors (called “angels”) put their own money into startups or start-up businesses. These investors often provide funds in the early stages of a company's development when access to traditional sources of capital (such as banks or venture capitalists) is limited. Angel investors typically provide money in exchange for a stake in the company or other terms such as convertible bonds (bonds that can be converted into shares in the company at a future date). Unlike venture capitalists, angel investors can take a higher risk because they often invest in businesses in the very early stages, when they do not yet have stable revenues or a proven business model. Among the advantages of angel investment for startups is not only financial backing, but also the investor's experience and contacts that can help the business grow. For the investor, on the other hand, this form of investment is a chance to get high returns if the startup becomes successful[1].

Angel investments are financial investments that private investors (angels) provide to startups in the early stages of development in exchange for a stake in the company. Angel investors may not only invest money but also help the startup with strategic advice and contacts, but their main goal is to capitalize on the investment in the future. Angel investors provide funds for business development in exchange for a stake in the company or other terms (such as convertible bonds). Angel investors expect a financial return if the business grows successfully (e.g. through an exit or sale of shares). Investors can support startups not only with money, but also with advice, experience, contacts, etc. Angel investments are high risk, but can also bring significant returns if the startup is successful.

Business angels have played a role in the formation of many modern corporations,

prime examples include Apple Corporation, Richard Kramlich was the first business angel to invest 22 thousand 500 dollars in Steve Jobs and Steve Wozniak's startup. In 1995, Jeff Bezos attracted 981 thousand dollars of investment in Amazon from 20 angel investors. The first investors in Google were Andy Bechtolsheim, founder of Sun Microsystems, and David Cheriton, a professor at Stanford University, who invested 100 thousand dollars each in the company. Corporations such as Microsoft, Dell and Intel also received support from business angels in the beginning of their development [2]. It is worth noting that all investment offerings in the U.S., including angel offerings, are by default considered "securities offerings" and are subject to registration with the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC), unless they fall under exemptions (Securities Act of 1933).

The European and American angel investment market is one of the most developed in the world. For example, in Europe there are such institutions and associations as the European Business Angels Association (EBAN) - one of the first associations, today supports the interests of about 20,000 early stage private venture capitalists, British PE&VC Association - The British Venture Capital Association, supports the private equity and venture capital industry, BVK (Der Bundesverband Deutscher Kapitalbeteiligungsgesellschaften ist die Stimme und das Gesicht der Beteiligungsbranche in Deutschland, The German Private Equity and Venture Capital Association e. V.). V.) - The German Private Equity and Venture Capital Association e.V., etc.

According to the purpose and nature of investing, angel investors are generally divided into personal (individual) angel groups, which are individuals who invest their own money, and special business angel groups, which are associations of investors who jointly invest in startups. The groups can be organized through specialized platforms or through personal networks. Unlike venture capital, angel investors are usually more interested in long-term support for entrepreneurs than in quick profits. Angel investors are similar to mentors and philanthropists in the nature of their relationship, and although the above may be associated with the development of startups, they differ in their nature, motivation and forms of involvement. Mentorship is support through knowledge and advice, philanthropy is philanthropic investment with no expectation of return, and angel investment is financial support for profit.

In nature, angel investment is very similar to venture capital, the only difference is that angel investment is usually received at the earliest stages of a company's development, when a startup is just beginning its operations or is in the product development stage. This may be at the seed capital stage (seed stage). Venture capital, on the other hand, is most often invested at later stages when the company has already demonstrated some success, has a proven business model and may require additional funding to scale (Series A, B and beyond).

Angel investors can be individual private individuals who not only provide capital, but can also help the startup with their expertise or network of contacts. Venture capitalists are most often large investment firms that provide not only money, but also support in

strategic management, business development and scaling [3].

The legal nature of angel investments depends on a variety of factors, including the jurisdiction in which they occur, the types of arrangements between the investor and the startup, and the form of the investment. In general, angel investments involve a number of legal aspects that govern the relationship between the investor and the venture. Investments from angel investors are often formalized through the execution of various agreements. In some cases, an angel investor may provide funds in the form of a loan, which the startup must repay after a certain period of time. However, instead of the standard repayment, the contract may provide for the debt to be converted into shares in the company (so-called convertible bonds). For direct investment in a company, it is possible to conclude a capital investment agreement, where the investor makes an investment in exchange for a share in the company's capital. In such cases, the investor becomes a shareholder or founder of the company. It is not uncommon in practice to find examples of shareholder agreements. Such agreements regulate the rights of investors and founders, including voting, profit distribution, sale of shares, etc. Depending on the form of investment, the investor may receive rights to a share in profits (through dividends), voting rights in the management of the company, or the right to participate in key decisions (e.g., in the case of venture capital startups). However, in the early stages, the investor often does not have much influence on the company's strategy unless the investor is a significant shareholder. The startup, in turn, is obliged to comply with the terms of the agreement, ensuring accountability for the investor and making sure that the funds raised are used effectively. In the case of convertible bonds, the startup is obliged to repay the debt if the bonds are not converted into shares.

Angel investments may require amendments to the company's articles of incorporation to take into account the new distribution of shares among shareholders and the rights of the investor. The inclusion of the investor as a founder or shareholder requires the signing of articles of association, which may stipulate the terms of the investor's participation in management or profit rights. Angel investments can have different legal forms depending on the structure of the transaction, such as equity financing where the investor provides money in exchange for shares or an equity stake in the company. There are also convertible notes, where the investor provides money in the form of a loan that can be converted into shares in the company in the future, usually when certain conditions are met (e.g. the next round of investment) [4-9].

The legal nature of angel investments also includes tax aspects. Some countries have tax incentives for angel investors to encourage investment in startups. For example, tax deductions on capital investments or exemption from capital gains tax on the sale of shares in startups. Angel investors typically take significant risks because many startups may not succeed. In a legal context, investor protection may include various aspects, including restrictions on the sale of shares (lock-up periods), where an investor cannot sell his or her shares for a certain period of time. The investor may also be entitled to regular

information about the company's financial situation and its development. In the event of liquidation of the company, the investor may have a pre-emptive right to a return of his funds. Thus, the legal nature of angel investments is complex and depends on the specific terms of the transaction, the jurisdiction and the desired rights and obligations of the parties. It is important that both the investor and the startup carefully work out all legal aspects to minimize risks and ensure mutually beneficial terms.

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